

EVALUATION OF THE BRAIN TOMOGRAPHY FINDINGS OF THE PATIENTS UNDER THE AGE OF 18 BROUGHT TO THE EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT WITH HEAD TRAUMA

Keywords

Head trauma,

Brain CT,

Trauma mechanisms,

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to learn the type of pathologies are detected in brain computed tomography (CT) performed in patients under the age of 18 who were brought to the emergency department with head trauma. Describing the common findings will increase the clinician's foresight, to evaluate the patient more quickly and to predict the risks that may occur.

This study was conducted in Department of Emergency Medicine- Hatay-Turkey. The study population consisted of patients who presented to the pediatric emergency department between January 1, 2018, and December 31, 2018, due to head trauma, and who underwent a brain CT scan. Findings listed as displaced and non-displaced fractures, epidural-subdural hematoma, sub-arachnoid hemorrhage, intraparenchymal hemorrhage, shift, edema, contusions, herniation, and pneumocephalus. The differences in tomography were evaluated by dividing the patients according to age groups. Data were recorded and analyzed by using SPSS version 22. The data obtained were presented in tables according to age ranges.

The study population consisted of 751 patients, n=508 (67.6%) males and n=243 (32.4%) females. When the trauma mechanisms of the patients were examined, it was seen that the most frequent cases were falling (n=516 68.7%). 9.2% of the patients had non-displaced fracture in 11.7% (88/751), displaced fracture (69/751), 4.1% (31/751) subdural hemorrhage, 2.7% (20/751) epidural hemorrhage, 2.9% (22/751) sub-arachnoids hemorrhage, 2% (15/751) intra-parenchyma hemorrhage, 6.4% (48/751) edema. Considering the mortality rates according to the CT findings of the cases, edema was present in the patients with the most ex. Following this, the highest ex rates were seen in displaced fracture, subdural hemorrhage and SAH, respectively.

According to the findings of study, the most frequent cause of death was traffic accident according to trauma mechanisms, male according to gender, brain edema according to CT findings, and 0-6 age group according to age.

INTRODUCTION

Head trauma in children constitutes a substantial proportion of patients presenting to emergency departments. In the United States, approximately 600,000 children under the age of 18 seek emergency care each year due to head injuries, with over 60,000 of these cases resulting in hospitalization. Furthermore, around 7,400 children lose their lives annually as a result of head trauma.^{1,2} Between 2000 and 2011, it was reported that emergency department visits for head trauma increased by 10%, while the proportion of patients with traumatic brain injury (TBI) requiring surgical intervention remained consistent.³ In Turkey, more than 290,147 pediatric patients are known to present to healthcare facilities due to head trauma. Additionally, this condition is associated with significant morbidity and mortality. Therefore, the early identification and appropriate management of children with severe head trauma by emergency physicians is of critical importance in reducing both morbidity and mortality.⁴ A detailed analysis of the common findings on brain scans of patients under 18 years of age will provide clinicians with valuable insights, enabling them to evaluate patients more efficiently and predict potential risks more accurately.

The popularity of SG is based on its relatively simple technical feasibility, lack of intestinal bypass, and lower risk of nutritional complications compared to other bariatric procedures (e.g., Roux-en-Y gastric bypass). Studies conducted worldwide have shown that SG provides significant

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study desing and setting

This retrospective study was conducted at the Emergency Department of Hatay Mustafa Kemal University Research and Application Hospital, a tertiary care facility (Level 1 trauma center) that receives approximately 100,000 patients annually, including around 5,000 trauma cases. Data were collected from the hospital's information management system (HIMS) for the period between January 1, 2018, and December 31, 2018.

Study population

The study included patients under 18 years of age who presented to the pediatric emergency department either by emergency medical services (112) or independently due to head trauma and underwent a brain CT scan. The decision to perform CT imaging was based on the PECARN (Pediatric Emergency Care Applied Research Network) scoring system. A total of 751 patients were included in the study: 508 males and 243 females. Patients were categorized into three age groups:

- 0–6 years (infancy and early childhood),
- 6–13 years (later childhood/primary school age),
- 13–17 years (adolescence).

Radiological evaluation

Brain CT scans were evaluated for the presence of the following findings:

- Displaced and non-displaced fractures
- Subdural hematoma
- Epidural hematoma
- Subarachnoid hemorrhage
- Intraparenchymal hemorrhage
- Midline shift
- Cerebral edema
- Contusions
- Herniation
- Pneumocephalus

Statistical analysis

The relationships between categorical variables were analyzed using Pearson's Chi-square and Fisher's Exact tests. Descriptive statistics for categorical variables are presented as frequencies and percentages. Statistical analyses were performed using the SPSS software, version 22.0, and a p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

The brain CT findings were evaluated for displaced and non-displaced fractures, subdural hematoma, epidural hematoma, subarachnoid hemorrhage, intraparenchymal hemorrhage, midline shift, cerebral edema, contusions, herniation, and pneumocephalus. Upon reviewing the CT findings of all patients, the following results were observed: 9.2% (69/751) had displaced fractures, 11.7% (88/751) had non-displaced fractures, 4.1% (31/751) had subdural hematoma, 2.7% (20/751) had epidural hematoma, 2.9% (22/751) had subarachnoid hemorrhage, and 2% (15/751) had intraparenchymal hemorrhage. Additionally, findings such as midline shift, cerebral edema, contusions, herniation, pneumocephalus, and trauma mechanisms are presented in Table 1.

According to our findings, the most common cause of injury was falls, followed by traffic accidents, blunt trauma, and gunshot wounds.

Comparison of Trauma Mechanisms Across Age Groups; The comparison of trauma mechanisms across age groups is detailed in Table 2. In all three age groups, falls were the most common trauma mechanism observed. Additionally, statistically significant differences were found across all trauma mechanisms with a p-value of <0.001.(Table 2)

Evaluation of Mortality Based on Age Groups, Gender, CT Findings, and Trauma Mechanisms; Table 3 presents an evaluation of mortality based on age groups, gender, CT findings, and trauma mechanisms. Our results indicate that the highest mortality rate was observed in the 0-6 age group, while the lowest mortality rate was found in the 13-17 age group. In terms of gender, the mortality rate was higher in males compared to females.

Based on CT findings, patients with cerebral edema had a higher mortality rate, followed by those with displaced fractures. Regarding trauma mechanisms, traffic accidents were associated with the highest mortality rate. (Table 3)

DISCUSSION

Throughout history, traumatic brain injury (TBI) has been one of the primary concerns for physicians in terms of patient evaluation and management. According to recent studies, the incidence of traumatic brain injury occurs every 15 seconds, while fatalities related to it occur every 12 minutes. Traumatic brain injury accounts for approximately 50% of all trauma-

related deaths. The advent and use of brain CT scans have revolutionized this field, serving as a crucial diagnostic tool and significantly influencing physicians' approach to patient care. Preventive measures and educational programs aimed at reducing the mechanisms of injury can help mitigate or even prevent such injuries. Numerous studies have been conducted in this area, although there remains a lack of sufficient research on this topic within our country. A review of the literature reveals that the majority of trauma cases involve males, with men being 2-3 times more likely than women to experience traumatic injuries.^{5,6}

Among the 751 patients included in our study, 508 (67.6%) were male and 243 (32.4%) were female. A study conducted by Kasmaei et al.⁷ in Iran found a gender distribution of 81.8% male and 18.2% female. Similarly, a study by Ratcliff et al.⁸ reported a male-to-female ratio of 79% to 21%. It is important to highlight that these studies, as well as the majority of the literature, predominantly involve adult populations. Overall, studies from various countries consistently show a higher incidence of traumatic brain injury (TBI) in males. In our study, the male population was approximately twice as large as the female population. The increased incidence of TBI in males, as compared to females, can be attributed to a range of sociocultural factors. These may include men's greater involvement in physically demanding jobs, their higher participation in riskier activities and violent confrontations, as well as the higher proportion of male drivers. Such factors contribute to the increased vulnerability of men to traumatic brain injuries.

A review of the existing literature on traumatic brain injuries reveals that most studies have focused on individuals within the 18-45 age range. In a study conducted by Tuncer et al.⁹ it was found that mild traumatic brain injuries were most prevalent in the 19-45 age group.

Akyel et al. reported an average age of 42±18 years among patients with traumatic brain injuries admitted to the neurosurgery clinic.¹⁰ In a study conducted in Pakistan, the highest incidence of traumatic brain injury was found in the 21-30 age group.¹¹ Salottolo et al.¹² compared patients above and below the age of 65, revealing that 73% of cases occurred in those under 65, while 27% occurred in those over 65. In our study, the distribution of patients by age group was as follows: 379 patients were in the 0-6 year range, 247 in the 6-13 year range, and 125 in the 13-17 year range. Studies investigating

pediatric populations have shown that traumatic brain injuries account for 50% of childhood mortality.¹³ Traumatic brain injuries can occur at all stages of life, from childhood to adulthood, and are caused by various factors. Andrade et al.¹⁴ argued that in cases of pediatric minor traumatic brain injury, the mechanism of injury plays a more significant role than factors such as isolated clinical signs, symptoms, the patient's age, or the time from injury to hospitalization in determining the medical management approach. According to a study by Efendioğlu et al.¹⁵ the most common cause of trauma was falls, accounting for 77.6% of cases. This was followed by traffic accidents and other causes, each accounting for 10.2%.^{16,17} In our study, we evaluated a total of 751 pediatric patients aged 0-17 years who presented with traumatic brain injuries. Upon examining the mechanisms of trauma, we found that the most common cause of injury was falls, accounting for 516 cases. A total of 125 cases were admitted due to traffic accidents, followed by 51 cases of blunt trauma and 50 cases of gunshot wounds. The concept of the "golden hour," referring to the critical importance of timely emergency intervention in patients with traumatic brain injury, is widely recognized.¹⁸ Traumatic brain injury tends to present with fewer clinical signs in pediatric populations. As a result, the use of imaging techniques, particularly CT scans, has become crucial for early detection of brain injury and for facilitating the safe discharge of patients with head trauma.¹⁹⁻²¹ To our knowledge, there is no study comparing the frequency of CT scans performed in emergency departments with those conducted in other specialties in our country. In a retrospective study conducted by Hacıoğlu et al.²² at Uludağ University in Turkey, a total of 2,321 patients were evaluated. The study found that cranial CT imaging was performed in 1,708 (71.46%) of the cases. Notably, soft tissue edema was not included among the CT findings in this study. The most commonly observed lesions were bone fractures, followed by subdural hematoma, subarachnoid hemorrhage, cerebral contusion, and epidural hemorrhage, with bone fractures being noted in 146 (6.11%) patients. Similarly, a study by Atmış et al.²³ in Adana reported bone fractures as the most frequent finding, followed by epidural hematoma. In another study by Ceylan et al.²⁴ epidural hematomas were the second most common finding, after fractures, on CT imaging. A large-scale investigation by Dayan et al.²⁵ involving 42,112 patients with traumatic brain injury focused specifically on children with mild traumatic brain injury who presented with vomiting. The

findings indicated that, in the absence of additional clinical signs beyond vomiting, performing a CT scan may not provide substantial clinical benefit on its own. Furthermore, Jennings et al.²⁶ demonstrated that, with accurate assessments in the emergency department and the adoption of updated guidelines, the rate of CT scans in children with mild traumatic brain injury could be reduced from 29% to 20%. In our study, all patients underwent CT imaging. The frequency of CT scans was notably higher in cases involving falls and traffic accidents.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the findings of our study indicate that the leading cause of death, based on trauma mechanisms, was traffic accidents. In terms of gender, males exhibited higher mortality rates. Regarding CT findings, cerebral edema was associated with higher mortality, and with respect to age, the highest mortality rate was observed in the 0-6 age group

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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Table 1. Findings on Brain Tomography of All Patients

CT Findings	n	%
Non deplase fracture	88	11,7
Deplase fracture	69	9,2
Edema	48	6,4
Subdural hemorrhage	31	4,1
Pneumocephalus	27	3,6
Contusion	26	3,5
Subarachnoid hemorrhage	22	2,9
Epidural hemorrhage	20	2,7
İntra parenchymal	15	2,0
Shift	6	0,8
Herniation	2	0,3

Table 2. Comparison of Trauma Formation Mechanism and Age Groups

rauma Mechanism	n	%
Fall	516	68,7
Traffic accident	125	16,6
Blunt trauma	51	6,8
Gunshot wound	50	6,7
Other	6	0,8
Blow	3	0,4

Table 3. Examination of age-gender groups in terms of mortality

Age group	EX			
	Yes		No	
	n	%	n	%
0-6	12	54,5	367	50,3
6-13	8	36,4	239	32,8
13-17	2	9,1	123	16,9
Gender				
male	16	72,7	492	67,5
female	6	27,3	237	32,5
CT Findings				
Edema	8	36,4	40	5,5
Deplase fracture	6	27,3	63	8,6
Subdural hemorrhage	5	22,7	26	3,6
Subarachnoid hemorrhage	5	22,7	17	2,3
Non deplase fracture	4	18,2	84	11,5
Intraparenchymal hemorrhage	3	13,6	12	1,7
Epidural hemorrhage	2	9,1	18	2,5
Contusion	2	9,1	24	3,3
Pneumocephalus	2	9,1	25	3,4
Herniation	1	4,5	1	0,1
Shift	1	4,5	5	0,7
Trauma mechanisms				
Traffic accident	8	36,4	117	16,0
Gunshot wound	7	31,8	43	5,9
Fall	7	31,8	509	69,8
Blunt trauma	0	0,0	51	7,0
Blow	0	0,0	3	0,4
Other	0	0,0	6	0,8

* p value Pearson chi square was obtained from the test.